

Improving Outcomes for Veterans Justice Outreach Patients

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Background

- Collaborative efforts from Veterans Treatment Courts and the Department of Veterans Affairs (VA) Veterans Justice Outreach (VJO) programming effectively reduced Veteran incarceration rates (24% to 9% from 1978-2012)
- VJO connects Justice Involved Veterans with mental health and substance use disorder to treatment
- There are no clinical practice guidelines for the special population of Justice Involved Veterans for mental health despite the elevated risk for suicide, overdose, and medical illness including HIV & Hepatitis

Aim & Purpose

- To introduce an evidence-based practice protocol to guide psychiatric nurse practitioners when providing care to Justice Involved Veterans. It was anticipated that the use of an evidence-based practice protocol would improve provider confidence and result in improved Veteran outcomes
- To increase rates of housing, employment, and decrease recidivism of JIV before and after the evidenced based practice education was provided to mental health group nurse practitioners

Methods

- Procedure and analysis**-Two phase quality improvement project
- NP understanding measured by pre/post test-using the adapted National league of Nursing validated tool, student satisfaction and self confidence in learning. (n=10 & n=12; unequal sample) evaluated by independent t- test and Levene's test for unequal variance
 - Follow up data 10 weeks after training with intent to continue at 6 & 12 months
 - Cohort isolated by electronic medical record query of VJO encounters using stop code 592 from 2020-2021 (pre-intervention(n=667) comparing rates of homelessness, employment, and rearrests in FY 2022 (post-intervention (n=180)

Sample and Setting

Sample- All patients in VTC/VJO program & all Mental Health department nurse practitioners were provided training
Setting- Southern California, VA Medical Center Outpatient Psychiatry Department

Conceptual Model

Pathway to Triple Recovery

- Effective substance use disorder treatment and overdose education/including naloxone
- Risk Needs Responsivity (RNR) model targeted case management
- Peer/social support
- Moral Reconciliation therapy and Motivational interviewing
- Safe space using Trauma Informed Care
- Suicide prevention
- Primary care- screening and treatment of chronic illness, or illness requiring vaccines

Triple recovery model inspired by Sacks et al., (2012)

Results

Veterans Justice Outreach Data from Fiscal Year 2020-2022

	Unemployment	Housing/Homeless
FY 2020		
NP	24%	36%
Other staff	21%	35%
Combined	22%	21%
FY 2021		
NP	9%	32%
Other staff	8%	25%
Combined	7%	29%
FY 2022		
NP	3%	3%
Other staff	0%	5%
Combined	3%	6%

VJO Veterans under that care of Mental Health NPs who received the training. No significance from data due to low power after intervention.

Limitations

- Abbreviated time frame for data collection prevented any significant change of Veteran's outcomes
- Number of providers educated; training was limited to NPs
- Participation in training and testing required to be both voluntary and anonymous
- Data accuracy is limited by the accuracy of ICD-10 codes

Discussion

- Providing expert mental health care while navigating the multifactorial landscape of various city, county, and state laws and policies requires additional training. This project showed that when educated on key variables, NPs felt more prepared to treat JIV
- When universal elements (e.g., risk assessment, psychosocial needs interventions, substance use disorder treatment, and common medical needs specific to JIV) are understood by staff members they are more capable of meeting Veterans needs.
- Communication with VJO specialists to understand the individual court expectations and norms can help providers with knowledge gaps
- The efforts to evaluate rates of recidivism were unsuccessful. Only one event of recidivism was found via ICD-10 coding, Believed to be caused by poor coding/human error. This highlights the importance of correct coding of encounters

Recommendations

- **Future implications**- This special population should be further evaluated for what works best to provide a full recovery from SUD/MH/Justice involvement
- Additional research is needed to understand outcome variables specific to female Veterans, as well as LGBTQ populations. Creative solutions are needed to provide optimized Trauma Informed care for those in very small numbers with VJO programming
- It is recommended that VA create nationally disseminated recommendations on the universal components of these best practice principles to be used by providers of mental health care working with JIV